

Bioremediation of distillery waste: An overview

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ABSTRACT

In the era of industrialization, effluent generation is a common factor while improper treatment of wastewater prior to discharge is a major concern. Due to the potent application of alcohol in medicinal, cosmetics, food, biochemical, chemical sectors distillery industries are growing rapidly throughout the world. It is considered as one of the most polluted industries due to its huge effluent volume generation, characteristics and presence of recalcitrant contaminants. Effluent from distillery industries has a great impact on environment due to its diversified pollutants concentration. The untreated distillery effluent easily finds access to watercourse thus causing eutrophication and ultimately imbalance the ecosystem. The unpleasant obnoxious odour, colour, low pH, high biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) values and presence of recalcitrant compounds poses several environmental and health issues. Hence, the main objective of distillery industry is to minimize waste generation through process modification in the manufacturing units. Several clean-up technologies are implemented for chemical and biological treatment processes. Potential microbial community, plant based remediation, enzyme technology and advancement in bioreactors are being explored to combat environmental pollution. On the other hand, valorisation and value added product recovery from the effluent is an emerging field for distillery effluent management. This review presents an overview of the generation pathway and nature of the distillery effluent, biological agents, enzyme technologies, role of microbes and biotechnological tools employed for treatment and option for the recovery of value added product.

1. Introduction

Upswing in the rate of population growth and industrialization contributes largely in the generation of huge amount of waste products in the environment in an imbalanced pattern. The amount of waste generated is proportionally increasing with the establishment of new industries. Urbanization and increasing demand of consumers, not only contributes in the amount of waste generation but also in the diversification of pollutants. It is predicted that by the year 2025, more than 60% of the global population is likely to suffer freshwater scarcity. On the other hand wastewater generated from different pumping stations of different cities passes through open channel causing contamination of neighbouring water bodies especially in pisciculture ponds (Kundu et al. 2016).

Wastewater is defined as water discharged from residential areas, industries, hospitals, agriculture lands, etc. It

can be categorized as i) domestic effluent coming from toilets (blackwater) and kitchens and bathing (greywater), ii) water from commercial establishments educational institutions, hospitals, hotels, restaurants, iii) industrial effluents from distillery, textiles, cosmetics etc. iv) stormwater from excess rain/snow fall. As increasing population growth demand more fresh water and create a gap between supply and demand of fresh water necessitating treatment of wastewater for reuse. Water is inevitable for life, agriculture, industry, aquaculture, etc. Proper treatment of wastewater can meet the future demand of water as well as safe from environmental point of view.

In India, every day about 38000 MLD (million litre/day) sewage is generated, while the facility for about 12000 MLD effluent treatments is available. Even the existing treatment capacity is not effectively utilized due to operation and maintenance problem. Based on the pollution intensity among all the sources of effluent generation, distilleries has

been considered as one of the 17 most polluting industries, as 80% of its raw materials can be converted into waste. The production of portable alcohol in distillery is based on the starchy crops (rice, wheat, barley, maize, corn etc.) and sugar-based crops (molasses), which are used as raw materials in distillery industries in Asia and South America (Sowmeyan and Swaminathan 2008). Use of raw materials varies from

country to country depending upon the cost, availability and carbohydrate content. Variation of raw materials in alcohol production is not a new concept. In ancient time name of the alcoholic drinks depended on the raw substrate used, preparation of starter culture and processing techniques (Das et al. 2017).

Table 1. Different raw materials used in 1G (first generation) and 2G (second generation) ethanol production with their by-products and value added products (El Mekawy et al. 2013).

Substrate	Major constituent/Byproducts	Valorised Products
1stG ethanol production		
Wheat	Gluten	Succinic acid
	Gruel	Amylase
	Starch	Biohydrogen
	Bran	Lactic acid
	DDGS	Cellulase, Vanillin, Ethanol
Barley	Brewer's spent grain	Biohydrogen
	Malt waste	Methane, Lactic acid, Citric acid,
	Bran	Amylase, Laccase
Sorghum	Bagasse	Ethanol, Biohydrogen, Butanol
Rice	Bran	Cellulase
	Bran oil	Lactic acid
Corn	Hull	Vanillin
	Flake	Ethanol
	Stillage	Methane
	Fiber	Protease
	DDGS	Succinic acid
	Cob	Butanol
	Stover	Ethanol
Steep liquor		
2ndG ethanol production		
Kans grass	Waste biomass	Ethanol
Pineapple leaf waste	Limonene	Biomanure
Citrus peel waste	Naringin	Biobutanol
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Lemon oil	Biomethane
<i>Lantana camara</i>		Vermicompost
<i>Bambusa bambos</i>		Cosmetics
Banana stalk		Xylitol
Sugarcane top		Acetic acid
		Ethylene
		Furfurals
		Glycolic acid
		Ethylene glycol
		1,3-Propanediol
		Propanoic acid
		Ferulic acid
		Vanillin
		Chitosan
		Fumaric acid
		Citric acid
		Ethanol
		Butanol
		Butanediol
		Lactic acid
		Acetone
	Sorbitol	

All over the world, approximately 61% of alcohol is produced from sugar crops. Molasses is the main feed material used in this process. Corn is the second most important starch-based crop, highly utilized in United States in ethanol production. In India, the first distillery industry was established in Kanpur in 1805 for military use only (Kharayat 2012). Now, in the present scenario, India has more than 325 distillery industries with total production of 3 billion litres of alcohol coupled with 45 litres of spent wash annually (Chowdhary et al. 2018a). Alcohol serves as basic chemicals in maximum number of chemical industries and also used as fuel, thus, there is a huge requirement to meet the demand. In order to meet the consumers demand more and more distillery plants have been established and simultaneously generating huge amount of wastewater daily. At IIT Kharagpur the researchers are engaged in the production of alcohol from starchy/lignocellulosic biomass which is coming under the 1G or 2G ethanol (Kuila et al. 2016; Avanthi and Banerjee 2016; Avanthi et al. 2017; Rajak et al. 2017). The present communication deals with the reported and practiced alcohol industries in India along with the other processes which are generally adopted in the normal/conventional practices in conjunction with the latest developed technologies.

Distillery industries produces 15 times more spent wash (liquid effluent generating from the discarded fermented mash) of the total alcohol production (Mohana et al. 2009). Generation and nature of effluent varied with the use of raw materials and addition of fermenter cleaning water, cooling water, boiler water, etc. (Pant and Adholeya 2007). However, spent wash has extremely high BOD and COD with low pH, high nitrogen, phosphorus, calcium and potassium content. Various types of organic and inorganic pollutants like polysaccharides, reduced sugar, proteins, and waxes are present in the effluent (Chowdhary et al. 2018b; Arimi et al. 2015). Recalcitrant nature comes from the presence of melanoidin, brown polymer, formed by Millard amino carbonyl reaction and act as a toxic substance for microorganisms used in treatment process. Due to low biodegradability, it persists in nature and enters into the environment. Some other recalcitrant compounds are caramel, anthocyanins, tannins and different xenobiotic compounds (Mohana et al. 2009). The nature of byproduct or slow biodegradable end-products is totally dependent on the characteristics of initial feed stock considered for alcohol production. Table 1 depicts the production of by-products along with valorised products with varied source of raw material used in portable and second generation ethanol production.

Considering the effluent characteristics, environmental consequences and effluent discharge guidelines, treatment of the distillery effluent are highly justified from environmental and societal point of view. Melanoidins, responsible for dark effluent colour where the dark colour represents major pollutants triggering serious environmental and health issues. In aquatic system, presence of recalcitrant organic pollutants causes endocrine disruption, hormonal imbalance and affecting reproductive fitness. Furthermore, presence of high organic load causes anoxic condition by depleting oxygen in the water and high nutrients concentration led to the eutrophic condition (Kamble et al. 2017). Some level of minerals and compounds showed long term effects like cytotoxicity and

genotoxicity (Chowdhary et al. 2018a). When discharged into the terrestrial area, it changes the soil pH, inhibits seed germination, reduces manganese concentration and damages crop production. On the other hand, the untreated biomasses upon consumption may lead to mortality, ill health effect and low milk yield of animals (Chowdhary et al. 2018b). Discharge of the distillery effluent in the soil affects soil microflora, interrupts nutrient cycle, changes sodium absorption ratio (SAR), soluble sodium percentage (SSP) and Kelly's ratio. Leaching of organic and inorganic minerals also affects the ground water quality by changing pH, conductivity and colour (Mohana et al. 2009). After scrutinizing the present pollution scenario of the country, the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) is making stringent policy measures to control the pollution level from distillery industries. Thus, treatment technologies are necessary by maintaining standard discharge criteria to protect environment as well as human being and to maintain ecosystem homeostasis. Though, there are several treatment options like physical, chemical, physio-chemical and biological, biotechnological routes are more promising from the environmental point of view and ease of application. The advancement in the treatment facility not only facilitates the cost effective treatment but also helps to meet the stipulated environmental demands.

The present paper deals not only on appropriate treatment processes of solids and semi solids waste treatment techniques but also focuses on strategic treatment policies with respect to the advancement in the bioreactor systems, wastewater generation and its appropriate treatment. Furthermore, it deals with the advantages of natural processes over existing practices where the importance of biotechnological approaches for utilizing enzymes and microbes are not only emphasised but also the impact of such processes is discussed.

2. Generation of distillery effluent

Expanding establishment of distillery plants together with population growth has led to an understanding of the relationship between pollution, environment and public health. Effluent generation from distillery industries poses severe environmental problems and generated waste needs to be treated optimally before releasing to the environment. Raw materials required for the production of 1G ethanol mainly uses sugarcane molasses, cereal crops, grapes, barley malt, etc. Cellulosic biomass is used as a raw material for the production of second generation (2G) ethanol.

Process of alcohol production is mainly divided into 4 steps: i) liquefaction, ii) saccharification, iii) fermentation, iv) distillation (Fig. 1). Liquefaction is the initial step, involves mixing of raw material with the water to make thick slurry. In saccharification step, amylolytic enzymes (amylase and amyloglucosidase) are added to the slurry. These enzymes help in breakdown of the starch releasing sugar molecules. In fermentation step yeast is added to the slurry containing tank. During this process conversion of sugar into ethanol takes place in the presence of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). Distillation is the final step which produces alcohol/spirit in equal proportion with biomass (distiller grains) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The effluent generated is

Fig. 1 A schematic representation of alcohol production and effluent generation in distillery plant

huge in quantity which is continuously getting discharged from the reactor tank. After distillation, the biomass is centrifuged to separate liquid and solids. Solid particles are dried at high temperature with the help of steam dryers and product is called Distillers Dried Grains with Solubles (DDGS). The drying process of effluent sludge restricts its contact with water bodies which is an advantage of this

process. A continuous effort is being given by the researchers to find new ways for valorization of distillery byproducts i.e. DDGS in different sectors such as animal feed formulation, polymer production, bio-adhesive, peptide generation, enzyme production, etc. (Singh et al. 2018).

Table 2. Raw material and its effluent characterization.

Raw Material	Parameter					References
	pH	BOD	COD	TOC	TS	
Sugarbeet, Mollases	3.0-4.1	30	-	-	51.5-100	Natraj et al. 2006
Wine/Grape	3.8	20	-	-	68	Tofflemire 1972
Beet	5.2	-	80.5	-	2.5	Jimenez and Borja 1997
Sugarcane	4.4	42.23	97.5	36.28	3.9	Martin et al. 2002

*TOC-Total organic carbon, TS-Total solids

Table 2 refers the various biochemical compositions of the agro-residues that are used for bioethanol production. Based on the major constituent of the initial raw materials, distillery effluents generation by the different industries with the adoption of the various treatment strategies is ending-up with the different byproducts. All such approaches to treat

distillery wastes/effluents result into the simpler compounds which can either be released into environment safely or can further be processed into valuable products such as CH₄ through anaerobic treatment method. The breakdown of distillery waste by different treatment technologies are mentioned below:

Chemical treatment:

Aerobic treatment:

Anaerobic treatment:

Table 3. Waste treatment technology adopted in different countries.

Countries	Treatment Methods	References
Asian Countries (Malaysia, Thailand, Indonesia, India, China and others)	Activated sludge process, aerated sedimentation, grit screening	Kazmi et al. 2005; Dhote et al. 2012
European countries (Spain, France, Germany, Poland, Italy and others)	Trickling filters, stabilization pond, activated sludge process	Bianchini et al. 2016
African Countries (Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, Ghana, Chile)	Grit chambers, activated sludge, sedimentation tanks, sand filters	Wang et al. 2013
American countries (USA, Argentina, Canada, Mexico, Brazil)	Anaerobic filters, constructed wetlands, sedimentation tanks	Rubio et al. 2007; Anda et al. 2018

3. Significant Treatments Strategies for distillery effluent

Treatment of distillery effluent is the prime goal of distillery industries. The contemporary treatment methods used to treat distillery effluent includes physical, chemical, physicochemical and biological methods prior to its disposal. The selection of treatment methods depends on a range of factors viz. treatment efficiency, treatment cost, local topography, climate, availability of land and public acceptance of the treatment. The technologies for the treatment of distillery effluent have been adopted, depending upon the availability of land, filler material for compost and mode of disposal (Table 3). In the following sub-sections various treatment processes has been discussed in detail.

3.1. Physical and Chemical treatment strategies

Physical treatment methods are designed to improve physical or outer properties of the waste. These treatments intend to decrease the surface area across which transfer of contained pollutants occur, detoxify any harmful constituents which are contained in the waste and to limit the solubility of contaminants. Ordinarily, sedimentation/flotation and filtration processes involve settling and sieving of the waste. Sedimentation of any particle has a very close relation with the density and size of the particle (Al-kizwini 2015). Flotation process replaces the sedimentation method for waste treatment when the particles which are to be separated out have density closer to that of the water hence it appears problematic to settle in average sedimentation basins and as a result takes lot of time for separation. Flotation is often used to treat wastes from distillery, leather, metal finishing, and pharmaceutical industries (Mavros and Matis 1992).

In chemical treatment process different compounds like chlorine (Cl_2), oxygen (O_2), ozone (O_3), and permanganate (MnO_4) are added to the wastewater to oxidize the distillery effluent components into carbon dioxide (CO_2), water (H_2O), inorganic matter, and other nontoxic products (Benitez et al. 2003). For a distillery effluent treatment, processes like coagulation and flocculation are rapidly and efficiently used to remove the suspended, inert and/or undesirable colloidal particles. Mohana et al. (2009) have reported that melanoidins can be decolorized by various physico-chemical treatments. Majority of these treatment methods are applied to remove colour either by concentrating the colour into sludge or by partial or complete breakdown of the colour molecules. Pikaev et al. (2001) reported that treatment of distillery effluent using iron sulfate ($\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$) as a coagulant results, 40% removal of wastewater pollutants. de Heredia et al. (2005) also achieved 55% reduction in COD by using integrated Fenton-coagulant/flocculation process in distillery wastewater treatment. In another study, addition of ferrous sulfate, aluminum chloride, calcium oxide, ferric chloride along with coagulants reduced the colour to 95%, 74.4%, 80.2% and 83%, respectively, while COD was reduced as 78%, 61.3%, 39.8% and 55%, respectively (Chaudhari et al. 2007).

In table 4, different distillery effluent treatment methods have been elaborated based on the organic loading. From that table it can be revealed that not only the organic carbon and nitrogen are getting converted to some valuable end products through the selected process based on the initial COD content of the feed material, but also some other parameters such as BOD, DO, TSS, TOC, VS and other biochemical macro/micromolecules are also being converted through the mixed culture anaerobic/microaerophilic fermentation process.

Table 4. Different treatment technologies based on organic loading employed for distillery effluent (Melamane et al. 2007).

Sl. No	Digestion reactor type	Organic loading rate
1.	UASB	19.0-24.0 kg COD/m ³ /d
2.	UASB	2.0-18.0 kg COD/m ³ /d
3.	Anaerobic filter and UASB	3.0-5.4 kg COD/m ³ /d
4.	Stirred anaerobic digester	0.55-0.75 g COD/gVSS/d
5.	Anaerobic granular sludge reactor	10.0 kg COD/m ³ /d
6.	Down flow fluidized bed reactor	1.8- 4.5 kg COD/m ³ /d
7.	Anaerobic up- flow fixed bed reactor	0.2- 18.0 kg COD/m ³ /d

Among the above mentioned methods it can be concluded that each technique is suffering from some shortcomings that has a great impact on social, economical as well as environmental impact. Mostly, advantages include complete removal of solids, better biomass retention, compact configuration of the plant, treating higher organic loadings, disinfection capability, nitrate removal, etc. Reclamation of water extends help in meeting stringent effluent discharge regulations.

At present, these processes being cost-effective are practiced in conventional way. But the nature of raw material and its volume of handling are huge. Thus, the waste generated after this process cannot be ignored which not only require a huge amount of water to neutralize but also creating a high BOD/COD containing effluent which has a great impact on liquid waste generation. This may be a concern for the present practices.

3.2. Biotechnological processes

The biotechnological treatment methods depend upon the natural growth and selection of microbes in a suspended culture or fixed film (Droste 1997). Distillery effluent needs to undergo intensive treatment in order to meet stipulated guidelines issued by the pollution control board. Application of physical and chemical methods are quite expensive thus, their employment in distillery industries are limited. On the other hand, biotechnological tools have gained much attention around the world for treatment of effluent and also helped the workers in developing proficient and cost-effective waste

treatment systems (Naik et al. 2008). Biotechnological treatment combines a range of engineering and scientific techniques for applying biological systems to manufacture or bioconversion of value added product or the elimination of hazardous substances which may be poisonous, toxic wastes (Henry and Heinke 1996). There are a number of waste treatment systems which are based on aerobic and/or anaerobic microbial action to treat high pollution load from distillery effluent (Willmott et al. 1998). On the other hand a preliminary anaerobic treatment method followed by aerobic treatment is suggested when BOD:N:P ratio is 100:2.4:0.3 of wastewater. For the high treatment efficiency three stage treatment methods is widely acceptable where initially anaerobic treatment has been implemented followed by aerobic treatment. In the first stage, anaerobic lagoon efficiently removes upto 85% BOD when detention time (DT) is 60 days with initial loading of 0.67 kg BOD/m³.day. In the second stage 65% BOD can be removed (DT 40 days) with initial loading of 0.15 kg BOD/m³.day. Further treatments can be carried out through aerated lagoons or oxidation ditches (Kharayat 2012).

Lettinga and coworkers (1997) reported that during treatment process of distillery sludge, microbes utilize pollutants for growth and simultaneously convert the organic substrate into simpler substances such as CO₂ and water, in the aerobic and anaerobic condition. Therefore, identification and optimization of suitable biotechnological treatment techniques is a need of the present day (Thakur 2006). The biotechnological treatment is broadly divided into 2 categories viz. anaerobic and aerobic treatments.

Fig. 2 A schematic representation of different types of biotechnological processes

3.2.1. Anaerobic treatment

Anaerobic digestion is a natural process in which various microbial species work mutually, in the absence of O₂. This process helps in conversion of organic wastes (industrial waste, kitchen waste, etc.) into biogas (Mata-Alvarez 2003). In a process of anaerobic digestion, biomass and biogas are produced, while pathogenic microorganisms and unwanted organic matter are reduced. Therefore, anaerobic digestion has 2 main advantages i.e., it can be used as a pollution control system and also can generate energy (Moletta 2005). Pretreatment is prerequisite for conditioning the effluent prior to treatment. Spent wash have a high temperature which may impact on ecosystem when directly discharge in aquatic body. Hence, temperature reduction is very much needed in spent wash. On the other hand, thermophilic treatment is one of the advanced treatment technologies used for the purification of high strength wastewater. It has ability to reduce COD to one-tenth when compared to other conventional wastewater treatment processes. This treatment process involves elevated temperatures i.e., above 45 °C to a maximum of 70 °C. Many microbial communities involving thermophilic anaerobes such as *Methanotrix thermophila*-related methanogens, *Desulfotomaculum* and related bacterial populations were the key members responsible for terephthalate degradation under thermophilic methanogenic conditions in a thermophilic anaerobic hybrid reactor (LaPara and Allman 1999).

It has several advantages over other conventional technologies such as it can tolerate high temperature waste composition, increases rate of degradation of organic matter, reduce the hydraulic retention time (HRT), have high removal efficiency of pollutants, those facilitate in the reduction of the sludge volume. Study with anaerobic mesophilic suspended growth reactor (AMSGR) showed biogas production from spent wash during its processing. Biogas of 16.9 L was produced with varied methane content 65% to 75% at an organic loading rates of 38-39 g COD/L. Simultaneous removal of COD, TS and VS were achieved by 52%, 40% and 46%, respectively in the final effluent (Banu et al. 2006).

Low pH value is another obstacle of spent wash treatment. Neutralization of the effluent helps in anaerobic treatment process. In neutral pH condition microbial community acts proficiently in the degradation of organic substrate and increase the yield of the recovered products. Basically, nutrients, alkalinity, suspended solids concentration in the spent wash lies within the microbial tolerance limit. But excess concentration of these parameters should be monitored for good anaerobic practice (Patyal 2015).

Anaerobic digestion of stringent effluent usually occurs in successive steps and is accomplished by four groups of bacteria (Ranade et al. 1999). These bacteria groups function in a synergistic relationship and form a food chain, in which the final products are CH₄ and CO₂. There are a number of microorganisms that are involved in the process of anaerobic digestion including acetogens (acetic acid-forming bacteria) and methanogens (methane-forming archaea). Anaerobic digestion involves 4 major biological and chemical stages: i) hydrolysis, ii) acidogenesis, iii) acetogenesis and iv) methanogenesis. Hydrolysis begins with the involvement of

water. Acid/bases act as a catalyst during this stage. In anaerobic treatment, enzymes like cellulosome, protease, etc. also play important role in breakdown of complex biopolymers (fatty acids, starch, cellulose, etc.) into simple monomers unit (peptide, amino acid, soluble sugar, etc.) in the presence of fermentative bacteria (Singh et al. 2019). Acidogenesis begins with breaking of monomers into volatile acids, alcohols etc. Acetogenic bacteria like *Clostridium* sp., *Lactobacillus* sp., *Actinomyces* sp., *Acetobacter acetii*, etc. are acid former bacteria and they attacks intermediates of acidogenesis (Das et al. 2018; Rastogi et al. 2018). Acetic acid, carbon dioxide and water are the main product of acetogenesis. Last step of anaerobic digestion is methanogenesis. *Methanosarcina*, *Methanobacterium*, *Methanobacillus*, *Methanococcus* etc. are some methane producing organism which acts on intermediate product of hydrolysis, acidogenesis and acetogenesis. A list of various microorganism are given in table 5 where, it has been mentioned the efficiency of microorganism to degrade and decolorized toxic chemical pollutants.

3.2.2. Aerobic treatment

Aerobic processes occur in the presence of oxygen and falls under category of biological treatment. The aerobic environment maintained in the bioreactor is achieved by implication of diffused or mechanical aeration, which maintain the mixed liquor in a completely mixed regime. Aerobic digestion is an alternative method of treating the organic sludge's produced from various treatment operations. In the conventional aerobic digestion (Coverti et al. 1993), the wastewater is aerated for an extended period of time in an open, unheated tank using conventional air diffusers, or surface aeration equipment (Hsu and Shich 1993). Aerobic treatment systems are used mainly to remove the BOD of these wastes. Partial reduction of BOD and COD is achieved in many distilleries using biological treatment (Jawed and Tare 1999; Laubscher et al. 2001).

The aerobic treatment of industrial wastewater usually depends on the oxidative activities of microorganisms. Although, a large number of microorganisms, such as bacteria, cyanobacteria, yeast, fungi, etc. have been used for treatment of spent wash. In aerobic process high oxygen supply rate to microorganism promotes the biochemical reaction as these processes have oxygen feed limitation. Phenolics compound in spent wash can be degraded by using filamentous fungi. Apart from those single or hybrid bioreactor has immense potentiality to treat distillery effluent where value added product recovery is possible along with effluent treatment in a conjugated manner. Sequencing batch reactor (SBR) system, contact stabilizer, trickling filter, microbubble aerator, etc. are some of the examples of aerobic wastewater treatment (Mondal et al. 2017). One major advantage of aerobic treatment method is that the process takes minimum time for stabilization and thus is faster in nature while compared to other systems.

Table 5. Microorganism enlisted for the COD removal of distillery effluent.

Class of microbes	Role of microorganism in distillery effluent treatment	COD removal (%)	References
Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonas, Klebsiella, Aeromonas, Acinetobacter</i> and <i>Enterobacter</i>	44	Ghosh et al. (2004)
	<i>Bacillus subtilis, B. anthracis, B. licheniformis, Achromobacter sp., B. thuringiensis, B. licheniformis, B. subtilis,</i> and <i>Staphylococcus epidermidis, Xanthomonas fragariae</i>	85–86	Chaturvedi et al. (2006)
	Mixed culture of: <i>B. thuringiensis, B. brevis, Bacillus sp.</i> (MTCC6506)	76	Jain et al. (2002)
	Acetogenic bacteria of strain No. BP103	63.39	Kumar and Chandra (2006)
		70.9	Sirianuntapiboon and Prasertsong (2008)
Fungus	<i>Phanerochaete chrysosporium</i>	48	Guimarãesa et al. (2005)
	<i>Trametes pubescens</i> MB 89	79	Strong and Burgess (2007)
	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> UB260, <i>A. niger, A. fumigatus</i> G-2-6, <i>A. Niveus</i>	69-75	Mohammad et al. (2006), Shayegan et al. (2004), Miranda et al. (1996), Angayarkanni et al. (2003)
	<i>P. chrysosporium</i> ATCC 24725	48	
Algae	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	61	Valderrama et al. (2002)
	<i>C. sorokiniana</i>	92.5	Solovchenko et al. (2014)
	<i>C. vulgaris</i> SR/2	83.2	Travieso et al. (2008)
	Mixed culture of green algae (<i>Chlorella, Chlorococcum</i>	55-60	Tarlan et al. (2002)
	<i>Chlamydomonoas, Pandorina, Eudorina,</i>		
	<i>Diatoms, Flagellates, Cyanobacteria</i> <i>Microcystis, Anabaena</i>)		

3.3. Role of bioreactors in treatment of distillery effluent

Waste effluent treatment involves physical, chemical and biological unit operation which is carried out in a closed vessels or tanks commonly known as “reactor”. A reactor provides a controllable environment enabling the biological, biochemical and biomechanical requirements to produce products (Singh et al. 2014). The standard types of reactors used for the treatment of waste effluent are: batch reactor, continuous flow stirred tank reactor - CSTR, plug flow reactor, complete mix reactors in series, upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor and fluidized bed reactor (Burghate and Ingole 2013).

3.3.1. Membrane bioreactor (MBR)

A MBR can be defined as a process that integrates the biological degradation of wastewater when coupled with membrane filtration (Cicek et al. 2001). The combination of membranes in the biological treatment of wastewaters was first reported by Smith et al. (1969). He used an ultra filter membrane to separate activated sludge from the final effluent left after distillation process. The recycling of the biomass in the aeration tank significantly reduce the BOD and COD content. Membrane bioreactor are of 3 types: i) solid-liquid membrane, ii) gas permeable membranes, and iii) extractive membrane. In solid-liquid separation process micro-filtration is used for recycling of biomass. The gas permeable membranes are used to diffuse oxygen mass transfer to the

degradative bacteria present in the bioreactor. The third type of membrane bioreactor is an extractive membrane that was designed for the transfer of degradable organic pollutants from distillery effluent, via a non-porous silicone membrane, to a nutrient medium for subsequent degradation (Schoerberl et al. 2005). These three different types of bioreactor can be assimilated together to built a customized hybrid bioreactor. According to Cornel and Krause (2006), micro-and ultra-filtration membranes is used for the separation of the activated sludge from the treated effluent, which removes solids particles and microbes resulting much higher biomass concentration.

3.3.2. Fixed film reactors

A stationary fixed film reactor has a biofilm support made up of activated carbon, PVC (polyvinyl chloride), hard rock particles or ceramic rings for biomass immobilization. The wastewater is dispersed from above or below the stationary media separating the coarse particles. Fixed film reactors have several advantages over other reactors because they have simple design, no mechanical mixing, good loading stability, accumulation of a large amount of biomass on the support media, high organic loading rates, high specific surface area and short retention times. The disadvantage of this reactor is that it gets clogged due to the formation of thick biofilm and high concentration of the suspended solid particles in the effluent. For treatment of distillery effluent,

Wang and co-workers conducted a novel four-stage step-feed wastewater treatment system combined with a fluidized bed laboratory experiment where, removal rates of COD and ammonia were 88.2% and 95.7% with effluent concentrations of COD and ammonia less than 50 mg/L and 8 mg/L (Wang et al. 2012). Fixed film reactors helps in reducing BOD level of effluent waste containing high solid loads (distillery waste). Treatment of distillery effluent by *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* (white-rot fungi) is an effective pollution controlling agent. Batch aerobic studies of the biological process showed that *Basidiomycete* can remove 83.15% COD, 85.70% BOD and 88.25% colour of distillery wastewater, respectively. Hossain (2007) used a 30% (v/v) inoculum of 7 day old culture for the effluent treatment. The optimum pH and temperature is 5.5 and 40°C, respectively for maximum pollution reduction. *P. Chrysosporium* can degrade maximum of COD, BOD and colour by 16 days of incubation at optimum condition. In another study, polyurethane foam-immobilised-fungus decolourised 10% diluted effluent by 60% and 73% by 5 and 7 days, respectively. The COD of the distillery effluent was reduced from 2255 mg/l to a final value of <150 mg/l (Jackson et al. 2007). The removal of COD using fixed film bioreactor for winery and distilleries wastewaters is very high, up to 95%, with organic loads between 5 and 15 kg COD/m³ of digester/day.

3.3.3. Upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor (UASB)

UASB technology is commonly used to treat effluents from various sources, such as distilleries, food processing industries, textile, tanneries and municipal wastewater. The active biomass in the form of sludge particles is retained in the reactor by direct settling for achieving high cost-effective designs. The advantage of using this bioreactor is that it is cost-effective in comparison with anaerobic filter or a fluidized bed system. The major disadvantage is it takes long time to get started and requires large amount of granular seed sludge to start faster. The distillery effluent and raw molasses wastewater were treated by laboratory-scale anaerobic upflow-fixed bed reactor, in which COD and BOD reductions were more than 75 and 85%, respectively, for wastewater samples (Seth et al. 2013). Treatment of wastewater that contains ethanol and acetate with UASB reactor obtained more than 80% COD removal efficiency (Zhaoqian et al. 2013). Treatment of winery wastewater was studied on three UASBs. The first reactor was inoculated with granular sludge enriched with *Enterobacter sakazakii* and reached a 90% COD removal within 17 d at HRT of 24 h, the second was inoculated by brewery granules and achieved 85% COD removal within 50 d, and the third was seeded with just sludge and showed the typical problems encountered with conventional sludge seeding and had to be continuously reseeded (Keyser et al. 2003). Treatment by a UASB reactor resulted in 90% COD removal when sugarcane molasses spent wash was used as a feed (Goodwin and Stuart 1994). Anaerobic digestion of malt whisky distillery feed was diluted before treatment due to the presence of sulfur compounds, potassium, calcium and free hydrogen ions left in solution after pH correction (Sanchez et al. 1885). More than 90% COD removal efficiency was found during study period

of three seasons in a UASB plant treating distillery wastewater (Wolmarans et al. 2002).

3.3.4. Anaerobic fluidized bed reactor

In this type of reactor, bed or media is used to attach microorganisms which support its growth and is driven by the drag force exerted by the upflowing effluent. These reactors perform in continuous state with uniform particle mixing and temperature gradients (Singh et al. 2014). The bed usually used in fluidized bioreactor is made up of sand or activated carbon. In fluidized state, the media/bed provides a large surface area for biofilm formation and growth. It supports high reactor biomass hold-up and promotes system efficiency and stability. Fluidized bed technology is more effective than anaerobic filter technology as it favours the transport of microbial cells from the bulk to the surface and thus, enhances the contact between the microorganisms and the substrate. An advanced anaerobic bioreactor popularly known as Hybrid Anaerobic Baffled Reactor (HABR) has been designed to treat distillery effluent with high efficiency. HABR works in a combination with anaerobic digestion and advanced oxidation. To the effluent sludge the anaerobic consortia is mixed in a reactor which decreases the BOD to almost zero level. The recalcitrant COD remaining after the first exposure with the reactor will be further broken down with help of suitable post oxidation treatment thus increasing biodegradability (Lekshmi, 2013). The advantage of using such kind of bioreactor is that they produce COD free colorless effluent which can be used for irrigation or recycled to conserve the water needs. Lekshmi reported that after treating effluent spent wash with HABR the COD of the raw spent wash was found to be around 82,000 mg/L which was reduced to 17,000 mg/L in the first stage. The biodegradability of remaining COD was increased by using hydrogen peroxide oxidation. Further it was again passed to another plug flow anaerobic reactor where the biodegradable COD is further reduced. Here the COD of HABR was further reduced to 6000 mg/L thus giving an overall COD removal efficiency of 92% at the end of the whole cycle of process (Lekshmi 2013).

Sometimes single treatment technologies cannot act as an efficient method to treat effluent of high organic load. Hence, hybridization of the existing techniques may be beneficial for efficient treatment. As for example comparative study on anaerobic hybrid (combining sludge blanket and filter) and UASB reactors for the treatment of spent wash established the efficiency of hybrid reactor. With the HRT of 5 days and OLR of 8.7 kg COD/m³/d, COD removal was higher by 1.06 folds in hybrid system than USAB treatment (Gupta et al. 2010).

3.3.5. Wetland

Wetland is an artificial constructed system that uses soil and organisms to treat distillery effluent, municipal sludge, industrial wastewater, greywater etc. Constructed wetland has been designed to remove organic constituents such as suspended solids, volatile matter and nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus. It utilizes a plant substrate (roots, stems and leaves) where microorganisms can grow and breaks down approximately 90 percent of pollutant present in distillery

sludge. Different plant species like *Eichhornia* sp., *Lemna* sp. and *Pistia* sp. are well established for contaminants removal from spent wash. Bama et al. (2013) reported upto 51.76% phosphate and 55.17% nitrate were removed through plant using in constructed wetland. *Typhalatifolia* and *Pennisetum purpureum* were successfully used in Horizontal Subsurface Flow Constructed Wetlands (HSFCWs), where average BOD and COD removal was 87% and 81%, respectively (Worku et al. 2018). Water hyacinth is reported as good accumulator of metals for its high uptake efficiency of pollutants. Presence of metallothioneins in the plant body helps to chelate formation of the metal thus separate metal from the polluted matrix. Work carried out by Bathla (2016) showed 62.80, 49.54 and 32.17, 36.84, 21.50 and 27.31% removal of iron, zinc, sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium from distillery effluent. Channel grass (*Vallisneria spiralis*) was implemented for the control of pH, EC, BOD, COD, TSS, TS, TDS, colour, Na and K in the distillery effluent (Singhal et al. 2003).

3.3.6. Hydroponics

Hydroponics is an emerging technology, highly used for distillery effluent treatment and could also facilitates vegetable production due to the presence of several important nutrients component in effluent. Hydroponics system ensures environment friendly food production through recirculation of wastewater. From the economic point of view this technology shows higher yield of fruits and vegetables, because of easy accessibility of nutrients, compare to soil system. Till now there are limited reports available on hydroponic system using distillery effluent. Hydroponic based nitrogen removal technology was implemented for cane molasses-based distillery effluent treatment where *Vetiveria zizanioides* and *Phragmites kharka* were established (Pant and Adholeya 2009). Aquaponics is another concept for wastewater treatment along with sustainable food production. Distillery effluent can also be treated by implementing this integrated technology where fish and plant can cultivate together in a quasi-closed recirculating system (Maucieri et al. 2018).

But before opting for hydroponics system, maintenance of the wastewater characteristics is important due to the nutrients tolerance limit of plant species. Limitation of different nutrients components in crop, fruits and vegetables production is a well-known fact. A typical nutrient characteristics present in wastewater for hydroponic system is established by de Kreij et al. (1999) is given in table 6. By observing raw effluent characteristics and nutrients limitation, dilution of wastewater for hydroponic system is essential. Bama et al. (2013) showed the effect of diluted distillery effluent on hydroponic system. Hence it is suggested to check and control the characteristics of distillery effluent before implementing in hydroponic system which can be achieved through preliminary treatment. Sometimes criteria should be customized with the cultivated plant species in the system. In recent time when “circular economy” is getting utmost important in waste management system, revenue generation from wastewater become an integral part. Recent trends is saying Global Hydroponics Market will be raised at a CAGR of around 6.4% and will reach at 13.73 US dollar by 2025 (www.Research and markets.com. (2017). In this circumstances, use of hydroponics or aquaponics technology will be a promising approach for distillery effluent treatment along with revenue generation.

3.4. Plant based treatment: Phytoremediation

Plant mediated pollutant removal facilitate low cost on-site and off-site treatment of metals and toxic organic substances, known as phytoremediation. The main advantages of phytoremediation lie on its selective uptake of pollutants by roots and accumulation and degradation by whole plant. Macro and microphytes have the potentiality to reduce BOD, toxic compounds, metals and total solid from the wastewater. High level of pollutant (~1000 ppm) accumulator plants is known as hyperaccumulator plant (Kundu et al. 2017). Some examples of metal accumulator plant species are listed in table 7.

Table 6. Limitation of wastewater components employed in hydroponic system.

Parameters	Unit	Concentration
Electrical Conductivity	ds/m	0.0.75
Biocarbonates	Ppm	0-120
Nitrates	mol/m ³	<0.5
Phosphorus	mol/m ³	<0.3
Potassium	mol/m ³	<0.5
Calcium	mol/m ³	<1.5
Magnesium	mol/m ³	<0.7
Sodium	mol/m ³	<3
Chloride	mol/m ³	<3
Sulphates	mol/m ³	<2
Boron	mmol/m ³	30

Table 7. Plant species involved in metal removal from wastewater.

Plant name	Metals removed
<i>Ambrosia artemisifolia</i> and <i>Apocynum cannabinum</i>	Lead
<i>Salix viminalis</i>	Cadmium, zinc and copper
<i>Nephrolepis exaltata</i>	Mercury
<i>Brassica juncea</i> , hybrid poplars grasses	Arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, and zinc
<i>B. juncea</i>	Cesium, lead, copper
<i>Melastomama labathricum</i>	Aluminum
<i>Pteridium culentum</i>	Arsenic
<i>Pteris vitata</i>	Arsenic, mercury, cesium and strontium
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Copper
<i>Silene vulgaris</i> and <i>Thlas picaerulescens</i>	Cadmium and zinc
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Arsenic and uranium
<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i> L.	Arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, mercury
<i>Brassica juncea</i> , pennycress, Alyssum sunflowers, hybrid poplars	Silver, cobalt, cadmium, chromium, mercury, manganese, molybdenum, nickel, lead, zinc, strontium, cesium, uranium

Phytoplankton, zooplankton are other organisms developed in distillery effluent help to stabilize the waste through phyto/bioremediation processes. In addition, a number of macrophytes are adapted with the distillery effluent for the efficient removal of metals and pollutants load. Thus there is a great opportunity to treat the distillery effluent apart from conventional methods using macrophytes and wetlands in low cost manner.

Microalgae are used widely in wastewater treatment. Capabilities of rapid and huge growth of both fresh and marine water algae in artificial condition make them more favourable in treatment technology. Moreover, these algae also have food value (Dash et al. 2016). However, they have the competence in biosorption and biodegradation of toxic chemical pollutants present in distillery spent wash. These toxic materials are polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), phenols xenobiotics, heavy metals, pesticides and melanoidins from distillery effluents. Various species of microalgae such as *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Oscillatoria boryana*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Phormidium valderianum*, *Nostoc muscorum*, *Neochlorisoleo abundans* and *Chlorella zofingensis* have been exploited in bioremediation of effluent (Maynard et al. 1999). Cyanobacteria, an oxygen evolving photoautotrophs are used to treat the solid waste and phenol containing distillery effluents and also reduce the BOD and COD levels (Shashirekha et al. 1997).

4. Value-added product derived from distillery effluent

Rapidly establishment of distillery industries are the evidence of growing demand of ethanol in various sectors. Billion litres of ethanol is been produced round the year thus generating huge amount of effluent which is diligent to manage. There is no misleading fact that ethanol industries are contributing their significant part in national economic growth, but generation of the waste can also be not ignored. However, it exerts considerable pressure upon environment and deteriorates natural resources available in ecosystem. Therefore, concept of recycling of waste to produce higher valuable product is required urgently. Researchers are continuously investigating new opportunities to develop a cost-effective process to

generate a value added products from distillery effluent. Nowadays, food and feed produced from the distillery waste is one of the most common selling product, established in the market. The solid spent wash is used as an animal feed additive, producing alcohol from corn, wheat and rice. Biomass collected from distillery is also used for biomethanation process to generate biomanure and fertilizer. Distillery effluent contains organic and inorganic nutrients having beneficial effect in increasing crop yields. Biogas is recovered with anaerobic fixed film reactors. In the present scenario, anaerobic digestion is gaining wider acceptance over aerobic treatment due to the production of biogas. In addition to this biopolymers and bioadhesive from DDGS is rapidly replacing petroleum based polymers. DDGS is also been used as a biofillers in production of composites thus making the product biodegradable and cost-effective. Current research is going on protein extraction from the distillery byproducts and its valorization in different biotechnological sectors.

5. Conclusion

Discharge of distillery waste poses severe damaging effects on environment including eutrophication, land erosion and deadly influence on ecosystem. Hence, prior treatment of the waste is becoming necessary before releasing/exposing into the surrounding/environment. Keeping in mind the detrimental effect of physico-chemical approaches of distillery effluent treatment and huge treatment cost motivated researchers to explore alternative cost effective and eco-friendly approaches through biotechnological means. Bioremediation, a green technology with more sustainability and specificity, holds a promising perspective in treatment of distillery waste. The emerging techniques like use of membrane bioreactor, fluidized bed reactor and anaerobic oxidation process embedded hybrid reactor have technological advantages over existing conventional techniques. Enzymes like oxidoreductases, hydrolases, lyases and microbes of mixed culture like *Bacillus* sp. and *Alcaligenes* sp. are actively being exploited in treatment of distillery effluent. Other methods like phytoremediation, aerobic and anaerobic digestion etc. have equally gained importance in effluent treatment and also make the process viable and by producing value-added product like

biogas. The utilization of the distillery byproducts produce higher value added product is one of the revenue generating perspective and can also impose positive effects on human health. After rigorous analysis of existing literature, a conclusion can be drawn that the use of single process alone may not treat the distillery effluent completely. Therefore, a combination of the methods like microbes integrated bioreactors, hybrid bioreactors, combination of one or more aerobic/anaerobic fermentation processes etc. integrated with byproducts may improve the overall process efficiency and profitability of the existing practices.

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